

Democracy Assistance Efforts of Young Donors from the Visegrad Group: In Search for Better Impact Evaluation Methods

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Abstract:

Until recently, the major donors in democracy assistance field were Western democracies and multilateral aid agencies; therefore the literature abounds with studies of aid coming from these donors. However, little is known about the effectiveness of democracy assistance from the young donor countries that not such as long time ago were recipient of this type aid. Much of democracy assistance work is done by civil society organizations that collaborate with partners in recipient countries within specific projects. How do these projects impact the beneficiaries of the project? How effective are these project in changing opinions and behaviors of the target groups? Finally, do they contribute to diffusing democratic ideas and behaviors? This paper demonstrates the shortcomings of existing impact evaluation methods to answer these questions and demonstrates the usefulness of randomization method that so far has been widely used in developmental aid.

Keywords: democracy assistance; impact evaluation; NGOs projects; young donors

INTRODUCTION: DEMOCRACY ASSISTANCE AND YOUNG DONOR PROGRAMS

The aim of this paper is to demonstrate why democracy assistance efforts of young donors need a new method of impact evaluation and how this new method, so far widely used in development assistance, could be the most credible tool to assess the impact of democracy aid.¹¹⁶

Democracy assistance is an effort of the governments and international organizations to support the spread of democracy as a political system in other countries. It was for a long time the domain of Western democracies (*e.g.* Alesina and Dollar 2000; Burnell 2000; Carothers

116 The term young democracies or third-wave democracies is used to contrast long-established Western “old democracies” and refers to a group of countries that underwent successful democratic transitions during the widespread, international push toward democracy, called the “third wave of democratization” (Huntington 1991). Thus, the term refers to those countries from regions such as Southern Europe, Latin America, East Asia, Southeast Asia, Central and Eastern Europe, and Sub-Saharan Africa that today are successfully consolidated democracies.

1999 and 2004; Diamond 1992; Lancaster 2007; Pinto-Duschinsky 1997; Ottaway and Chung 1999; Schraeder, Hook and Taylor 1998; Youngs 2006 and 2008). Thus, the literature has been usually focusing on democracy assistance programs run by quasigovernmental and nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), foundations, and international organizations. The major actors examined in the literature are the European Union, the United States government-funded and privately run US-based non-profit organizations and private donors as well as the Western European governmental in quasi-governmental donor agencies.

However, recently young democracies that were recipients of this type of aid not such as long time ago, like the EU new member states from the Central Eastern Europe (especially those belonging to the Visegrad Group), became active in the field of developmental cooperation and democracy promotion.¹¹⁷ The assistance programs of these young donors, which are growing and being institutionalized¹¹⁸ caught scholars' attention. Scholars have investigated approaches, reasons for a young democracy's engagement, methods to provide aid, and promote democratic ideas and practices, either focusing on one young democracy's efforts (Drażkiewicz-Grodzicka 2013; Pospieszna 2010a; 2010b; 2014) or exploring the whole region (Lightfoot 2010; Lightfoot and Szent-Ivantiyi 2014). From these studies we learn how government and social actors in a young democracy conceptualize developmental cooperation and democracy assistance and how their view on giving aid is different from approaches used by Western donors. Then, how a former recipient country goes about assisting other states in their struggles for democracy are investigated. The studies unveiled the key role of nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) in shaping the state's democracy assistance and their unique ability to reach civil society groups in recipient countries. This research also revealed a great potential of cross-border civil society networks in diffusing democratic ideas and behavior.

These studies motivated me to ask the question of how democracy assistance efforts by a young donor can be evaluated in terms of their potential to diffuse democracy to other recipient countries. The question addressed in this work arise largely from ongoing debates in the literature on democracy promotion regarding approaches and effectiveness of strategies used to assist recipient countries with their struggle for democracy. However, this study also engages many other literatures in political science. Some of them lie at the intersection of comparative politics and international relations—specifically research on democratization and democratic consolidation (Tilly 2007), and the role of external actors in these processes (Huntington 1991; Pridham, Herring, and Sanford 1997; Whitehead 1996), as well as on regional diffusion of democracy (Bunce and Wolchik 2006; Brinks and Coppedge 2006; Kopstein and Reilly 2000; Rogers 1995; Tarrow and della Porta 2005).

117 The Institute of Public Affairs, a Polish think tank based in Warsaw, together with their collaborators provides some overview of different democracy assistance programs run by the Czech Republic, the Slovak Republic, and Hungary. See for example "Democracy's New Champions" by Kucharczyk and collaborators published by PASOS (Policy Association for an Open Society), available at <http://www.isp.org.pl/files/8118721720517207001225798020.pdf>. Specifically on the Czech Republic see "The Czech Republic's Democracy Promotion Policies and Priorities" by Vladimír Bartovic available at http://www.europeum.org/images/paper/bartovic_isp.pdf.

118 Some institutionalized ways to provide aid by Visegrad group countries include Polish Aid by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Czech Transition Promotion Program by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Slovak Aid at the Ministry of Foreign and European Affairs of the Slovak Republic, and the Department for International Development Co-operation (DIDC) at the Hungarian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, as well as Visegrad Fund.

In order to answer the question of how democracy assistance efforts by a young donor can be evaluated I would like to follow up on research regarding the role of civil society organizations in democracy assistance and to suggest evaluating the project of NGOs in donor countries in the field of democracy assistance. However, because of difficulties in measuring the impact of democracy assistance projects, this study suggests to focus on projects that are targeted at specific target groups, e.g. young people. The choice of youth is motivated by the fact that this is very popular target group in democracy assistance, and because the outcome of project directed toward young people can be measurable. The paper suggests using Randomized Controlled Trails (RCTs) method of impact evaluation, the usefulness and novelty of which is described in this paper.

1. RCTS AND PROBLEMS WITH IMPACT EVOLUTION OF DEMOCRACY ASSISTANCE

The majority of research regarding the impact of democracy assistance and on civil society development and democratization in recipient countries refers to the Western assistance—governmental and non-governmental aid from the United States, Britain, Germany, and elsewhere in Western Europe—provided in the 1990s to Central and Eastern European countries (Ballentine 2002; Burnell 1996; Siegel and Yancey 1992; Quigley 2000; Wedel 1999) and to Russia (Richter 2002; Henderson 2003; McMahon 2004; Mendelson 2001). Despite the enormous interest and good will of foreign assistance donors, as well as the overall role in fostering democratization in recipient countries, scholars criticized the strategies used by donors which contributed to failure, limited results; or—in some cases—even paradoxical effects of foreign aid. Since young democracies joined the club of donors only recently, there is no research evaluating the impact yet. I argue that randomization method will improve the evaluation efforts thus providing a more accurate answer to the question whether democracy assistance works and under which circumstances.

The problem with findings regarding the impact of democracy assistance is that they cannot be comparable. First, there are very mixed results coming from a substantial literature focusing on democracy assistance in a particular country, or on a particular type of democracy assistance in a particular country or region. Second, there have also been works looking at multiple countries trying to draw conclusions about broader findings on program impacts.¹¹⁹ Finally, there are only a few using large cross-national quantitative analysis examining the effect of USAID democracy assistance on democracy building.¹²⁰ The results coming out of this research present interesting insights, but are far from being conclusive, and they cannot be comparable, because scholars tend to use different measures of impact, and different measures of democracy success. Moreover, scholars tend to adopt different qualitative and quantitative methods, which still are unable to precisely determine how much any observed changes can be linked to democracy assistance programs. If the country slides back toward

119 For example, Carter et al. (2003) study the overall impact of USAID programs in six countries; O'Neill (2003) demonstrates lessons from human rights assistance in various regions; and focusing on post-conflict countries: Pouligny (2005) critically examines the impact of international programs that go to civil society, and de Zeeuw and Kumar (2006) edited volume gives conclusions and recommendations based on different types of democracy assistance (media, human rights, and election programs) in nine postconflict states.

120 Azpuru et al. (2008); Finkel et al. (2007); Tusalem (2012).

authoritarianism amid large volumes of democracy aid, we still know little about whether all the money that donors are putting into civil society organizations matter, and about the effectiveness of specific democracy assistance projects implemented by NGOs' projects.

There is also surprisingly little systematic and comparative evidence on what works in democracy assistance among NGOs and donors.¹²¹ This is mainly because there are not good impact evaluation methods employed. NGOs and donors are more likely to use process evaluations in which investigators study how the project is implemented and what outcome can be observed. However, this method cannot determine whether key outcomes can be attributed to NGOs' democracy assistance project. Only recently there is a greater interest among national and international assistance agencies in better understanding "what works and what does not and why" but mainly in case of programs supporting economic development, health and environment.¹²² If practitioners know which projects work best and why and when, scarce resources for democracy may be used more effectively.

Given the problems with impact evaluation methods used by the scholars as well as practitioners (NGOs and donors) randomization method seems to be the most credible and accurate form of impact evaluation, and the best procedure to gain knowledge regarding the effect of assistance projects.

Why using RCTs to Evaluate the Impact of Democracy Assistance? The method of RCTs has been popularized especially by a group of economists in the Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab (J-PAL) founded at the MIT Department of Economics in 2003 which tests and improves the effectiveness of programs and policies aimed at reducing poverty.¹²³ However, impact evaluations in the area of democracy assistance using randomized design are lagging behind the evaluation of development assistance.

According to the proponents of this method, a proper impact evaluation includes efforts to establish the effects of some interventions relative to what would be observed in the absence of such interventions. This requires: 1) collection of baseline data, 2) collection of appropriate outcome data, and 3) and collection of the same data for comparable individuals, groups or communities that did and did not receive the intervention. As such, impact evaluation helps determine what would have happened in the absence of the program. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) method, also known as random assignment studies, randomized fielded trials, social experiments, or randomized design, is the most credible and accurate form of impact evaluation, the best procedure to gain knowledge regarding the effect of assistance projects. In development assistance some efforts have been done to estimate the difference before and after data of selected individuals, groups and communities that did not receive assistance in order to estimate what would happened in the absence of such aid.

121 See for example <http://fsi.stanford.edu/docs/215>

122 There are several aid agencies that initiated some new strategies for evaluating the effectiveness of its programs but only in the area of development assistance: USAID's Strategic and Operational Research Agenda (SORA), the Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation (NORAD), the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA), the Danish Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Germany Agency for Technical Cooperation (GTZ), and Development Impact Evaluation (DIME) by World Bank. However, the greatest weakness in evaluation studies has been the lack of reference or comparison group to help establish whether other trends and external conditions, rather than USAID's programs, were responsible to the observed outcomes.

123 For more information about this research centre see <http://www.povertyactionlab.org/about-j-pal>

2. RULE NUMBER ONE IN RCTS: MAKE IT MEASURABLE

The problem with impact evaluation in democracy assistance is that evaluations lack consistent logical framework that carefully specifies inputs, outputs, outcomes and impact, which undermines good evaluation, as the recent report by National Research Council (NRC) points (NRC 2008). Also, there are not many studies that undertake these efforts mainly due to difficulties in measuring the impact of projects. However, these challenges can be overcome if impact evaluation is carefully designed before the project begins according to the following steps.

First, in order to evaluate democracy assistance of young democracies using RCTs it is important to focus on a specific area of democracy assistance. The literature on democracy assistance distinguishes between four main areas of democracy assistance: election assistance (promoting more genuine and competitive elections and political processes), human rights assistance (strengthening respect for human rights), media assistance, and increased development of a politically active civil society (promoting youth activism, women empowerment).¹²⁴ Because most of this assistance is channeled through non-governmental organizations, because of their potential to reach civil society groups in their country or in aid recipient countries, it is legitimate to focus on donor-sponsored NGOs projects in a specific area.

Interestingly, young donors recognize the support for young people as one of the main targets in democracy assistance. Young people groups have demonstrated their democratizing potential and the Ukrainian youth group *Pora*, which played a crucial role in the protests in Ukraine and which had received funding from external actors, may serve as a good example. Young people also become an important civil society group to work with especially in authoritarian countries where cooperation with civil society organizations is restricted. Polish Aid program run the Polish Ministry of Foreign Affairs, for example, have financed many projects by Polish NGOs that aimed at activating young people abroad.¹²⁵

After choosing specific NGOs projects like those targeted at young people, the next step would be to, as NRC's report suggests, to answer the questions (such as: What is the target? What are their needs? What is the program seeking to change? What is the precise program or part of program being evaluated?), and to create a logical framework—i.e. inputs, outputs, outcomes and impact of the NGOs projects targeted at specific group.

Having clearly defined logical framework, the third step in determining the impact of donor-sponsored NGO projects would be to include before and after measurements on key outcome variables and measurements on both the group receiving the treatments and control of comparison group that would be not included in NGOs' programs. In case of NGOs projects targeted at young people, the *Treatment Group* would be the group of young people who would participate in the project by random selection, and *Control Group* would include those young people that through randomization will not participate in the project. Then, after the end of the project (the treatment) measurement on the desired outcome should be taken for both groups. If there is a difference in outcomes between the groups, it can reasonably be inferred that the difference was attributable to the project.

124 See for example Carothers (1999 and 2004), Kumar (2006).

125 To mention just a few like: "Transforming Care and Educational Youth Centers in Ukraine", "Active Youth – the Future of Ukraine", "Together Again – Youth Exchange Program," or "Polish-Ukrainian Youth Exchange." Polish NGOs project in this area also are funded by external donors, such as the National Endowment for Democracy (NED) or specifically by the programs meant to support young people like the YOUTH Program within European Commission's DG Education and Culture.

CONCLUSION

Inspired by the group of economists in Poverty Action Lab, in this paper I suggested using a method of Randomized Controlled Trails in impact evaluation of democracy assistance. It is believed that this method may help solve the problem of causal attribution of specific outcomes to NGOs' project in democracy assistance. This has not been done in democracy assistance field yet. Therefore with this novel method, this study may be a real breakthrough in evaluating donor-sponsored NGOs project in recipient countries, thus contributing to practice.

Nevertheless, by suggesting this new method of impact evaluation in democracy assistance, the study aims to build better knowledge about the effectiveness of democracy assistance, thus contributing to theory. Moreover, answering the question of effectiveness of young donors from Central and Eastern European region to provide democracy aid may contributes to the body of research on explaining observable democracy diffusion in the region (Bunce and Wolchik 2006; Jacoby 2006).

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